

Tumor Recurrence at the Colostomy Site: A Rare Case Report and Literature Review

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Abstract

Recurrence at the site of a colostomy is a rare event, though it has been documented in the literature. The time to development of carcinoma at a colostomy site after the initial diagnosis varies, ranging from 5 months to 35 years post-surgery, with a median of 22 years. This condition is generally associated with a poor prognosis.

We report the case of a patient who initially underwent colostomy for an obstructive left-sided colon adenocarcinoma. This was followed by radical surgery with clear resection margins. Despite this, the patient later developed a recurrence at the site of the former colostomy.

The recurrent mass was surgically removed, including excision of the lesion and re-excision of the surgical margins. In this case, the most plausible explanation for the recurrence is direct invasion of the abdominal wall by tumor cells.

This case highlights the importance of regular follow-up and thorough examination of stoma sites, as there remains a rare but significant risk of tumor recurrence in these areas.

Introduction

Tumor recurrence of colorectal adenocarcinoma at the site of a previous colostomy is a rare and unusual clinical occurrence. We present the case of a 38-year-old patient who underwent surgery for colonic adenocarcinoma and subsequently developed a tumor recurrence at the site of the initial diverting colostomy just five months after the primary operation.

The Case

We report the case of a 38-year-old patient who initially underwent surgery for a sigmoid colon adenocarcinoma. A diverting colostomy was first performed, positioned upstream and at a distance from the tumor. Two months later, the patient underwent definitive surgical resection of the tumor.

Intraoperative exploration revealed a prolapsed mass at the colostomy site, which was found to be adherent to the abdominal wall. As a result, the surgical procedure included a sigmoidectomy with en bloc resection of the tumor and the adherent parietal tissue, followed by colo-colic anastomosis and closure of the original colostomy site.

Histopathological examination of the resected specimen showed a 5.5 cm moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma with clear colonic and parietal resection margins. However, lymphovascular and perineural invasion were present. Adjuvant chemotherapy was recommended, but the patient did not adhere to the treatment plan.

Five months after surgical resection, the patient presented with a budding mass at the site of the old colostomy scar. The mass was mobile relative to the deeper tissues and measured approximately 5 cm along its longest axis (Figure 1).

To assess the extent of the lesion and to rule out other sites of recurrence, a thoracoabdominopelvic CT scan was performed. Imaging revealed a localized parietal mass without evidence of distant metastases or additional secondary lesions (Figure 2).

The patient's case was reviewed during the multidisciplinary team (MDT) meeting at our institution. A consensus was reached to proceed with carcinologic resection of the parietal mass, followed by referral for adjuvant chemotherapy.

More Information

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Figure 1: Picture of the Mass at the Ancient Colostomy Site

Figure 2: CT Scan of the Mass

The patient underwent surgical resection of the mass under local anesthesia. A circular incision was made around the lesion, ensuring oncologic safety margins. Intraoperative dissection revealed that the tumor was superficial, with no extension beyond the subcutaneous tissue. A re-excision of the surgical margins was carried out (Figure 3).

Histopathological analysis confirmed the mass as a moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma with clear margins. The closest margin measured 1.3 cm. The excised specimen, measuring 6 × 5.5 × 1.3 cm, showed no residual tumor tissue (figure 4).

Postoperative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on postoperative day one (D+1). At one-year follow-up, there were no clinical or radiological signs of local recurrence or distant metastases.

Figure 3: The Re-Excision of the Surgical Margins was Carried Out.

Figure 4: The Mass after Resection and the Specimen of Ee-Excision

Discussion

Recurrence of colorectal adenocarcinoma at a colostomy site is a rare clinical event. The first such case was described by Morgan in 1966 [1], and since then, only a limited number of cases have been reported in the literature [2]. These recurrences may present either as cutaneous metastases or as metachronous primary tumors [3].

Cutaneous metastases of colorectal cancer occurring on surgical scars following resection are uncommon, representing approximately 0.6% of all recurrence cases [4]. On average, skin metastases appear 4.9 years

after the initial diagnosis of colon cancer [5]. Unfortunately, the prognosis remains poor, with a reported average survival of 7.5 months following the appearance of skin metastases [6].

Distant metastases or tumor recurrence typically result from hematogenous, lymphatic, or direct spread of malignant cells. Several hypotheses have been proposed to explain the rare occurrence of carcinoma at the colostomy site. Vijayasekar et al. [7] suggested that residual micrometastases in lymph nodes along the inferior mesenteric artery pedicle could contribute to recurrence. Takami et al. [8] proposed a transformation from undetected polyps to adenocarcinoma, implicating overlooked synchronous lesions. Saegusa [9] introduced the theory that carcinoma at a stoma site may represent de novo metaplasia arising in the peristomal skin.

In our case, the development of the tumor mass is likely attributable to the aggressive and invasive nature of the local disease, which expanded to involve the abdominal wall. Despite complete carcinologic resection with histologically clear margins, residual microscopic tumor cells may have remained at a distance and, in the absence of adjuvant chemotherapy, could have proliferated. Moreover, chronic skin irritation at stoma sites is another recognized factor that may predispose to tumor development in this area.

The interval between initial diagnosis and the development of carcinoma at a colostomy site varies widely in the literature, ranging from as early as 5 months to as late as 35 years postoperatively, with a median reported interval of 22 years [10]. Most stoma-site carcinomas are diagnosed at an advanced stage [11]. Interestingly, tumors occurring at ileostomy sites appear to be reported more frequently in the literature than those arising at colostomy sites [11].

Currently, there is no standardized consensus on the optimal management of such rare recurrences. However, complete surgical resection with negative margins (R0 resection), followed by adjuvant chemotherapy, is generally recommended to minimize the risk of local recurrence or distant metastatic spread [2].

Conclusion

The appearance of a tumor at the stoma site is a rare event, and may be related to tumor recurrence or skin metastasis. Adenocarcinomas of the colostomy site may occur after the end of the postoperative follow-up period, highlighting the importance of continuous patient monitoring and inspection of the stoma site.

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